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Diversity and trophic structure of soil communities under climate change

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Abstract

This document represents a deliverable communication by the EJP SOIL internal project 'MINOTAUR' about the diversity and trophic structure of soil communities under climate change, based on the analysis of simple or composite bioindicator. Using collected data in MINOTAUR project from LTE field campaign and additional literature review data, the objectives of this document are i) to present different biological simple indicators and composite indicators, selected with the aim to better link soil biodiversity to associated soil functions and ecosystem service provisioning, and ii) to assess their response to climate change. The evaluation of the impact of climate change on soil communities, characterized by diversity or trophic structure, is possible by assessing the distribution of species that are likely to adapt to the changes in temperature and precipitations predicted by climate change scenarios. However, this approach has a number of weaknesses, mainly due to the mosaic pattern of land use. Another way to assess the effect of climate change on soil organisms, is to mobilize data, but this requires access to long chronosequences of data which is rare. In this document, results include i) three composite indicators (EI, QBS-ar, QBS-e) and one simple indicator (earthworm), and their answers in the different climate contexts from the MINOTAUR's LTE, ii) the response of earthworm community (abundance, biomass, diversity) at European level covering different climate contexts. The analysis of the composite indicators demonstrated i) the massive impact of land management rather than climate (precipitation, temperature) in the community structuration and by consequences on soil functions, ii) the complementarity of biological indicators to reflect environmental pressures and by consequence the necessity to integrate these different bioindicators, linked to different functions, in soil health assessment. The analysis of earthworm community (abundance, biomass, diversity) at European level reinforced the strong effect of soil properties and land use in earthworm community structuration, while demonstrating some sensitivity of earthworm abundance to climatic factors (precipitation and temperature).

While the MINOTAUR project is closing to date, it is the ambition of the authors to publish the results of some part of this study in a peer-reviewed journal. As such publication would appear under its own DOI, the raw data used in the analyses will be published as supplementary information in the journal, and to avoid further duplication are not available in association to this Zenodo deposited document. When published, the DOI of the paper will be provided here in an update.

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1. Introduction

This document represents a deliverable communication by the EJP SOIL internal project ‘MINOTAUR’ about the diversity and trophic structure of soil communities under climate change, based on the analysis of simple or composite bioindicator linked to soil functions. Using collected data in MINOTAUR project from LTE field campaign and additional literature review data, the objectives of this document are i) to present different biological simple indicators (earthworm community) and composite indicators, selected with the aim to better link soil biodiversity to associated soil functions and ecosystem service provisioning, and ii) to assess their response to climate change.

The evaluation of the impact of climate change on soil communities, characterized by diversity or trophic structure, is possible by mobilizing data, but this requires access to long chronosequences of data which is rare. Another way is possible to reason in terms of the distribution of species, i.e. habitats, that are likely to adapt to the changes in temperature and precipitations predicted by climate change scenarios. However, this approach has a number of weaknesses, mainly due to the mosaic pattern of land use. Indeed, agro-ecosystems in Europe are distributed in a mosaic pattern where sealed soil such as streets or lakes and the presence of refugia, such as hedgerows, grooves, patches of bushes or woodlands — wherever the pressure of farm operations is suspended — are interspersed. This aspect, when related to the range of movement of the micro-, meso- and macroscales through which edaphon is distributed, shows that the simple distribution of a particular species is not always able to give an indication of the variation of soil health, especially if this species is not correlated with the ecosystem functions of agro-ecosystems. Instead the assessment of whole communities could be more resistant to spatial changes, as the remaining available ecological niches are filled by other species. This is also due to the incredible diversity of soil species, which according to recent estimates account for about 59% of global biodiversity (Antony et al 2023) and the countless number of endemisms.

2. Method

Different biological indicators linked to soil functions were selected. Their response were analyzed at European level using data from LTE assessed in MINOTAUR project (Aponte et al., 2024) or data from big data set from WP2 of MINOTAUR project (Murugan et al., 2024). Synthesis of these parameters is presenting Table 1.

Table1: List of indicators and associated soil organisms and dataset

Indicators	Soil organism	Data set
EI	Nematods	LTE- MINOTAUR
QBS-ar	Microarthropods	LTE- MINOTAUR
QBS-e	Earthworm	LTE- MINOTAUR
Abundance	Earthworm	Database -MINOTAUR Earthworm
Biomass	Earthworm	Database -MINOTAUR Earthworm
Diversity	Earthworm	Database -MINOTAUR Earthworm

3. Results

3.1 QBS-e applied at LTE scale

Description of the index : QBS-e (Soil Biological Quality Index based on earthworms) is a composite indicator associated to earthworm community, based on the attribution of ecological categories (Paoletti et al., 2013)- Epigeic small earthworms, pigmented, living and feeding in the litter, with scarce digging capacity (i.e. *Lumbricus castaneus*); - Endogeic earthworms, less pigmented, living and feeding in soil, digging mainly horizontal burrows (i.e. *Aporrectodea caliginosa*); - Anecic and/or deep-burrower earthworms, large earthworm, digging vertical burrows up to a few meters in depth (i.e. *Lumbricus terrestris*), but often rise to the surface to feed on litter (i.e. *Octodrilus complanatus*); - Coprophagic earthworms, living and feeding in manure or compost and closely associated with a high content of raw OM (i.e. *Eisenia fetida*); - Hydrophilic earthworms, living and feeding in damp soils, river bottom and shallow water-table soils (i.e. *Eiseniella tetraedra*). In complement to these ecological categories, the QMS-e takes into account the growth stage of the earthworms, based on the presence or not of clitellum : immature and adult. An EcoMorphological score (EMI) is attributed to each ecological category and age (Table 2) based on their capacity to leave in agriculture context, their survival rate, their body mass and their habitat (litter vs soil profile) and their action on soil functions (dynamic of organic matter, burrowing and casting activities) (Table 2)

Table2: EcoMorphological (EMI) scores attributed to each ecological category and age (Paoletti et al., 2013)

Ecological category	Age	EMI score
Hydrophilic (HYD)	Immature (Im)	1
Hydrophilic (HYD)	Adult (Ad)	1
Coprophagic (COP)	Immature (Im)	2
Coprophagic (COP)	Adult (Ad)	2
Epigeic (EPI)	Immature (Im)	2.5
Endogeic (END)	Immature (Im)	2.5
Epigeic (EPI)	Adult (Ad)	3
Endogeic (END)	Adult (Ad)	3.2
Anecic/Deep-burrower (ANE)	Immature (Im)	10
Anecic/Deep-burrower (ANE)	Adult (Ad)	14.4

QBS-e obtained in the different sites showed a huge variability within sites and between sites: while the highest values were observed in LTE from Switzerland and Sweden, leading to Excellent soil quality, the lowest values corresponding the sufficient Soil Quality, were observed in three LTE presenting very different climate conditions (Italy, the Netherlands, Slovenia). These results suggested that climate conditions had less influence compared to soil properties and management.

Table 3: mean of QBS-e and standard deviation from the different LTE assessed in MINOTAUR and the attribution to Soil Quality class from Paoletti et al., 2013

	LTE						
	ACO1	AGROSCOPE	CREA	SLU1	SLU2	ULBF	WUR
	France	Switzerland	Italy	Sweeden	Sweeden	Slovenia	Netherlands
QBS-e	940 ^a	1035 ^a	102 ^a	1018	993	229	201
ET	492	457	73	386	486	119	100
Soil Quality class	Good	Excellent	Sufficient	Excellent	Good	Sufficient	Sufficient

The influence of management was demonstrated (Figure 1) but without any clear influence of mechanical action (standard tillage vs reduced tillage vs no till) neither fertilization type (mineral vs organic) (figures 2).

Figure 1: QBS-e values obtained in the different LTE, under different managements: RT=reduced tillage, ST= standard tillage, NT= no till; MN= mineral fertilization, OG= organic fertilization

Figure 2: mean QBS-e values obtained under different managements: RT=reduced tillage, ST= standard tillage, NT= no till; MN= mineral fertilization, OG= organic fertilization, in MINOTAUR's LTE

3.2 Nematods index, microarthropods index, earthworm at LTE scale

Result. The results (Aponte et al., 2024) showed that indices based on the weight of groups in relation to trophic function or adaptation to soil life (i.e. fungivores and bacteriovores nematodes, epi-emi- and eu-edaphic microarthropods, epigeic, anecic and endogeic earthworms) better discriminate tillage effect than traditional richness. Also the abundance of individuals, which - like bacterial respiration - can provide indications of the functionality of a soil but cannot, however, measure the loss of soil biodiversity, had generally resulted in more individuals being detected in the LTE with minimal or reduced tillage compared to standard tillage.

Furthermore, a Kendall correlation (figure 3) showed that the indices assessed were not in correlation, this state that every index leded different information and response to tillage, suggesting that is important not to simplify soil biodiversity monitoring to an excessively small set of indexes.

Figure 3: correlation between different simple or composite indicators assessed in MINOTAUR' LTE

3.3 Earthworm community (abundance, biomass, diversity) at European scale

Method: To assess the impact of climate parameters at European scale on earthworm community (abundance, biomass and species richness), the biological response to a large predictor variables was assessed, based on the large dataset issue from collection of existing data (MINOTAUR dataset). The data was analyzed using gradient boosting decision trees (CatBoost). The resulting models were 10-fold cross validated, and used to calculate SHAP values, which illustrated in detail the result of the gradient boosting and allowed to quantify the impact of the various predictors in an easier to interpret way.

Results

Table 4 highlights the most and least important predictors, as well as the intermediate ones, and Figure 4 displays the SHAP values (= negative or positive contributions to predictions in the unit of the response variable) in relation to the original values of the predictor to illustrate their relationship.

While we did not find precipitation and temperature among the most important predictors affecting earthworm communities in Europe, they were still in the intermediate category, which warrants a closer look at them. Figure 4 illustrates these relationships in more detail. While there are some clear trends regarding the effect of precipitation and temperature in the abundance and species richness models, the biomass model is less clear. This is likely due to the smaller sample size in the biomass model, and that the model explains the least amount of variation compared to the abundance and species richness models. Due to this, the biomass model will be subsequently disregarded.

Regarding precipitation, there is a clear trend, that both earthworm abundance and species richness predictions are generally positively affected by higher precipitation, while lower precipitation leads to negative contributions to predictions. This is not surprising, given the earthworm's known sensitivity to moisture conditions.

Regarding temperature, the trends are once again less clear, this time especially for abundance. However, for both abundance and species richness the trends are positive, with higher temperatures being associated with positive effects towards earthworm abundance and species richness predictions. In the abundance model any negative effects of temperature occur around a yearly mean temperature of 10°C, which is generally found in central Europe. Since a majority of data points originate from this area, the effects are likely coincidental, especially given the fact that several other predictors were more important than the climate variables. Similar arguments can be made for the species richness model, where the trend is stronger but similar to the abundance model.

However, since these models are based on long-term climatic data (reference period 1991-2020) and the data points themselves originate both from a time before, during, and after this reference period, we cannot for certain relate these effects to climate change as well. This proves a major limitation of these models.

In any case, given that there are several predictors which are more important than the climatic ones, this provides hope that any negative effects of climate change on earthworm communities may be able to be mitigated through beneficial management measures, such as providing fertilization, and improving bulk density and C/N ratio of the soil.

Table 4: Overview of importance of various predictors belonging to categories climate, soil, and agriculture on earthworm abundance, biomass, and species richness. Green = among the top five (=most important) predictors. Red = among the bottom five (=least important) predictors. Yellow = predictors of intermediate importance.

Category	Influencing factors	Earthworm abundance ($R^2 = 0.66$)	Earthworm biomass ($R^2 = 0.48$)	Earthworm species richness ($R^2 = 0.63$)
Climate	Precipitation (long-term mean 1991-2020)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
	Temperature (long-term mean 1991-2020)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Soil	Soil type (WRB)	Yellow	Green	Yellow
	pH	Yellow	Yellow	Green
	Soil texture	Green	Yellow	Yellow
	Soil organic matter	Yellow	Green	Yellow
	C/N ratio	Green	Green	Green
	Bulk density	Green	Green	Yellow
Agriculture	Land use	Red	Red	Green
	Organic vs conventional farming	Red	Red	Red
	Pesticide use	Red	Red	Red
	Fertilizer use	Green	Yellow	Green
	Tillage or grazing method (depending on land use)	Yellow	Yellow	Red
	Crop rotation	Red	Red	Red
	Crop	Red	Red	Red
Other	Earthworm sampling method	Green	Green	Green

Figure 4: Dependence plots of mean precipitation and temperature of earthworm abundance (A), biomass (B) and species richness (C) models. Black lines indicate trends in case of continuous variables, and black triangles indicate means in case of categorical variables.

4. Conclusion

This study which assesses the diversity and trophic structure of soil communities under climate change, based on the analysis of simple or composite bioindicator linked to soil functions, shows that using the available data (from LTE, from WP2-MINOTAUR dataset) climate change does not figure the soil biodiversity structure, while land management as well as soil parameters have a strong influence. The analysis of earthworm community (abundance, biomass, diversity) at European level reinforce the strong effect of soil properties and land use in earthworm community structuration, while demonstrating some sensitivity of earthworm abundance to climatic factors (precipitation and temperature). Our study also highlights the complementarity of biological indicators, simple or composite, to reflect environmental pressures and by consequence the necessity to integrate these different bioindicators, linked to different functions, in soil health assessment. The different composite indicators we have used were limited to some taxa and in this study focusing on soil fauna. There will be a real interest to develop a larger composite bioindicator, integrating microorganisms and micro-meso and macrofauna in order to cover larger functions.

5. Perspectives

While the MINOTAUR project is closing to date, it is the ambition of the authors to publish the results of some part of this study in a peer-reviewed journal. As such publication would appear under its own DOI, the raw data used in the analyses will be published as supplementary information in the journal, and to avoid further duplication are not available in association to this Zenodo deposited document. When published, the DOI of the paper will be provided here in an update.

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